

A Bibliometric Analysis of Smart City in The Subject Area of Physics

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Abstract

A bibliometric analysis of the field of smart cities is presented in this article, with a focus on identifying the top-cited articles and analyzing their bibliometric characteristics. The articles that include the term 'smart city' in the title were searched in SCOPUS, resulting in the identification of 801 documents. The top 100 most cited documents published between 2012 to 2022 were analyzed quantitatively in terms of publication trends, document type, and keyword co-occurrence. The 'Author's Keyword' and 'Index Keyword' were visualized using co-occurrence analysis. The top 10 most cited documents were qualitatively analyzed and found that the issues related to air quality and air quality monitoring, are also essential components of smart cities. This analysis aims to reveal major developments and trends in the field, contributing to the methodologies and hypotheses of future studies.

Keywords: Smart City, Physics, Bibliometric Study, Highly Cited, Publication Trends

1. INTRODUCTION

Smart cities are revolutionizing our view of the world and their functioning achieves a very high level of integration coordination, and cooperation between ordinary objects, providing them with some degree of intelligence [1]. The main concept behind a smart city is the assimilation of the physical world with the virtual world [2]. The goal is, in general, to make better use of resources in cities [3]. A lot of studies are currently being conducted in the area of “smart city” and physics subject area. These studies have written about the connection between “smart city” and other scientific fields, including data mining [4], Information and communication technologies (ICT) [5], the Internet of things (IoT) [6], and Machine learning (ML) [7].

Bibliometric analysis is a powerful tool for quantitatively investigating scientific outputs [8]. Researchers need a bibliometric tool to quantitatively evaluate scientific output in the “smart city” research area. Bibliometric analysis is the process of extracting measurable data through statistical analysis of published research studies, which can provide researchers with an important message in a specific field [9]. Bibliometric studies analyze research productively, top-cited publications, country scholarly outputs, most frequent keywords, and the trend of publication, and explore quantitatively the specific research area [10]. There are some bibliometric studies in the “smart city” research area, such as “A bibliometric review of smart cities and migration” [11] and “A bibliometric analysis on smart cities related to land use” [12]. However, from one side, none of these studies directly concentrates on “smart city” in the subject area of physics. On the other side, the previously published studies have not treated the bibliometric approach in the field of the top 100 most cited articles to the best of our current knowledge.

The current study aims to explore the research status and publication trends in the “smart city” field; thus enabling researchers to grasp the historical developments and current research hotspots of this field in the physics subject area. To achieve this aim, both bibliometric and content analyses of the existing literature

were carried out. The main objective of this study is to recognize and analyze top-cited research papers in the “smart city” field to find a path for future study. This bibliometric study aims to assess the role of the “smart city” and answer the research questions by collecting data from well-known scientific databases. The study seeks to answer the following three research questions (RQs);

- RQ1: What are the publication trends?
- RQ2: What are the most used index keywords?
- RQ3: What are the research hotspots?

2. METHODOLOGY

The study followed the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) flow diagram [13] to collect data, as shown in Figure 1. Data were obtained from the SCOPUS database on October 16, 2022, covering the period from 2012 to 2022. Figure 1 displays the search sets used in each step of the search, with the first search focusing on the subject area physics and its related search terms listed as "Search #1" in Figure 1. The top 100 documents were selected based on the number of citations per year (TCpY), representing the most highly cited papers among 801 documents. To conduct a quantitative bibliometric analysis, the VOSviewer software was used [14], which identifies emerging keywords in a specific area of research. The bibliometric analysis using VOSviewer included mapping of co-occurrence of keywords. Finally, the top ten documents were chosen for qualitative analysis. Two independent authors screened the titles and abstracts of the top 10 documents for extracting the main themes. The qualitative analysis involved a detailed evaluation of the selected documents, with a focus on themes and patterns that emerged from the data.

Figure 1 Search strategy flow diagram

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

There may be some limitations in the data collection procedure of this study, similar to other bibliometric studies. There are two main scholarly databases Web of Science (WoS) and SCOPUS. The data for this study was collected from the SCOPUS database. Therefore, there might be some documents on WoS that were not included in the dataset. However, SCOPUS provides more coverage than WOS [15]. Table 1 shows the distributions of 801 document types of “smart city” in the physics subject area. The majority of the 801 documents were journal articles and conference papers, 686 (%85.77) out of 801 documents. The number of conference papers was a little bit higher than journal articles. This indicates that the research in this area is still relatively new, and more publications are being dedicated to exploring new ideas on this topic. It could be assumed that once the number of journal articles and book chapters surpasses the number of conference papers, this will be a sign that the research in the field is becoming more established.

Table 1 Document type for the "Smart city" data set

Document Type	NO.	Percentage
Conference Paper	381	47.57%
Article	306	38.20%
Book Chapter	46	5.74%
Review	31	3.87%
Editorial	15	1.87%
Conference Review	10	1.25%
Other	12	1.50%

PUBLICATION TRENDS

Smart city research is an area of study that is becoming increasingly popular in recent years. The publication trends and the cumulative number of publications are shown in Figure 2. There is a clear trend that the number of documents dedicated to "smart city" research is growing. The annual number of documents dedicated to "smart city" research did not have obvious changes in the years 2012 to 2016, remaining at less than 34 documents per year. The cumulative number of documents dedicated to "smart city" research in the year 2016 was 66, and this number increased to 801 by the year 2022. This demonstrates significant growth in this area. The annual number of publications reached a maximum of 160 documents in the year 2021. The data were collected on October 16, 2022. Therefore, the number of publications in the year 2022 shows the tenth-month trends, which reach 136 documents. It is worth noting that the trend appears to be increasing in the years 2017 to 2021. This could be related to a higher level of awareness of and research into “smart city” topics. The growth of the number of documents dedicated to “smart city” research can be seen in the increasing number of publications from year to year.

Figure 2 Number of publications per year and the cumulative number of publications in the research area from 2012 to 2022

KEYWORDS CO-OCCURRENCE ANALYSIS

Keyword co-occurrence analysis is employed to identify and explore leading and emerging topics in the “Smart city” research area. Analyzing the co-occurrence frequencies of the keyword in publications can provide comprehension into main topics and research trends [8]. Co-occurrence analysis is based on the speculation that two items appear in the same context when they are related to some level. The VOSviewer software has the ability to visualize the outcomes of the co-occurrence frequencies of the keywords [16]. The 801 documents provide 385 SCOPUS “Author’s Keyword” and 935 “Index Keyword”. Figure 3 illustrates SCOPUS “Index Keyword” co-occurrence network in the “Smart city” research area. The yellow color shows leading and emerging topics in the research area. Keywords’ different colors indicate the initial date of their related publications, and the lines show the co-occurrence links between different keywords. “Air quality”, “Air quality monitoring”, and “Deep neural networks” were some of the most emerging topics in “smart city” research area.

The top 20 out of 385 “Authors’ Keywords” were divided into 3 distinct clusters: red (cluster 1); green (cluster 2); and blue (cluster 3) each cluster represented by a different color on the map (Figure 4). Cluster 1 contained the most significant number of keywords with 9, followed by 6 keywords in cluster 2 and 5 keywords in cluster 3. Analysis using the VOSviewer software showed that the most frequently occurring phrase in all clusters was the “smart city” (cluster 1) keyword with 76 occurrences and 86 total link strength, as expected. The second most frequent keyword, which belongs to cluster 3, was “internet of things” with 46 occurrences and 73 total link strength. The items from a cluster prove the considerable interest in the possibilities of coming together. For instance, long-range (LoRa) which also appeared in cluster 3, is a wireless technology that can help cities overcome network coverage challenges and enable them to widely deploy IoT solutions in smart cities [17].

Figure 3 Overlay visualization of “Index Keyword” (The figure available online [here](#))

Figure 4 Cluster view of “Author’s Keyword” network (The figure available online [here](#))

QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS

In order to identify research hotspots the top 10 documents with the most citations per year were selected for qualitative analysis. The top 10 documents which received over 10 times citations per year (TCpY) were selected for qualitative analysis. The title and abstract of the top ten documents were read by at least two co-authors separately and extracted the important themes. The final results were written after some careful discussions on the selected themes. Table 2 illustrates research hotspots highlighted in the top ten documents. The majority of high-ranked publications prove the finding of keywords co-occurrence analysis. Many of these top papers were focused on the potential of advancing existing technologies to further the potential of smart city development.

Table 2 Research hotspots highlighted in the top ten documents

NO	References	TC	TCpY	Urban science	Technology development	Sensing technology	Air pollution and health	Internet of things(IOT)	Sustainable energy	Transmit information	Power network
1	Batty et al. [18]	1177	107	X	X						
2	Hancke et al. [19]	385	35		X	X					
3	Huang and Kuo [20]	315	28.64				X				
4	Alavi et al. [21]	176	16					X			
5	Kitchin [22]	175	15.91	X							
6	Wang et al. [23]	153	13.91						X		
7	Le et al. [24]	144	13.09						X		
8	Ji et al. [25]	131	11.91					X			
9	Leccese et al. [26]	124	11.27							X	
10	Morello et al. [27]	112	10.18		X	X					X

(TC=Time Cited, and TCpY=Time Cited per year)

10. CONCLUSIONS

The advancement of technology and the integration of digital infrastructures have shaped our landscapes and cities, leading to the trend of smart cities. Smart city development brings with it a new set of challenges and opportunities; to understand them, comprehensive research is necessary. This article presents a short qualitative and quantitative analysis based on the published scientific literature on "smart city" in the subject area of physics. Analyzing the distributions of 801 documents collected from the SCOPUS database based on a title search of "smart city" in the physics subject area, indicate that the research in the smart city subject is still a relatively new field. The top 100 most cited documents focused mostly on urban development in cities by introducing the smart city model. Assessing the overlay visualization of "Index Keyword" and various clusters in the SCOPUS "Author's Keyword" co-occurrence network allows for the identification of the leading and emerging topics in the "Smart city" research area which were "Air quality", "Air quality monitoring", and "Deep neural networks" beside of internet of things. The selection of the top 10 documents with the most citations per year provided researchers with a valuable tool to identify research hotspots. Qualitative analysis of the titles and abstracts of the top 10 documents led to the identification of several

important themes related to smart city development. These themes ranged from urban science and sustainable energy to Air pollution and health and the internet of things (IoT) use. This article is helpful for future researchers to concentrate on the research hotspots in the “smart city” field. Additional research can be conducted to find the appropriate correlations between different topics.

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